

THE POWER OF ENGAGING “THE MILLENNIAL”

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Abstract

While the current world talks more about the characteristics, attitudes, behaviors that are exposed by the Generation Y workforce there is also a need that exists by default to have a better engaging mechanism for this segment of workforce as they are different from there earlier generations. This study aims at the need for engaging the generation Y in the organization.

Keywords: *Generation X, Generation Y, Engagement*

Introduction

In any organization today the major workforce are engineers and senior engineers who are typically less than 30 years old these workforce will be approximately 60% of the total workforce and they are called as “The Millennial” since they are born between 1982 and 2000. As there are more and more people entering year on year in the organizations it’s a must for the organization to understand their needs, generation differences, cultural difference, attitude, behavior and characteristics towards the work and create a better engagement strategy for them to make a better workplace.

- 80 million boomers will retire over the next 20 years
- There are only 43 million Gen Xers
- The 72 million Gen Ys will therefore dominate the workforce for 40 years.

Engaging “The Millennial”

Engaging “The Millennial” is one of the key elements for any organization as they need to ensure that the organization keeps up its engagement at a high level to ensure effective productivity and efficient performance. Though every organization utilizes various tools to boost the morale and engagement of the “the millennial” but yet HR and Internal Communications team have very limited tools to measure the impact of the morale and engagement of the employee.

Figure 1 : Employee Engagement Matrix

High Knowledge and High Behavior	-	Highly Engaged Employees
High Knowledge and Low Behavior	-	Actively Dis-Engaged Employees
Low Knowledge and High Behavior	-	Moderately Engaged Employees
Low Knowledge and Low Behavior	-	Least Engaged Employee

Least engaged employees are the one who creates disrupts in the organization, the engagement strategies that the organization creates show focus on all types of employees any engagement strategy that deployed its easy to pull the engaged employee as they always look for opportunities to participate more but the successful strategy is the one which pulls all segment of employees.

For organizations seeking to optimize their return on revenue, the topic of employee engagement and its impact on organizational performance is well known. With roots in organizational climate research (Schneider, 1985) and reinforced by service profit chain articles in Harvard Business Review (Heskett, Jones, Loveman, Sasser, & Schlesinger, 1994; Rucci, Kirn, & Quinn, 1998), the topic of employee engagement has captured the hearts and minds of senior executives and organizational psychologists alike because of its important role in promoting organizational effectiveness.

The Most Important Drivers Of Engaging “The Millennial”

- ❖ Is organization valuing my contribution
- ❖ Does the company has outstanding future (How the recession is handled in the past)
- ❖ The vision of the company should motivate
- ❖ Is the job offers me to use the skills and abilities and to develop it
- ❖ Is there a open culture and feeling to be part of a team.
- ❖ The leadership should be trustworthy
- ❖ My opinions are taken and valued
- ❖ There should be open communication.
- ❖ My manager
 - Is an outstanding leader who acts a guide, mentor and a coach
 - Need managers who speaks my lingo
 - Give me feedback then and there (Instant Feedback but in private)
 - One who can guide in right direction
 - Who is energetic and can work in my pace
 - Appreciate my efforts and results
 - Be as a guide , coach and a mentor
 - Who is not biased (typically well balanced)
 - Who is open and transparent?
 - Who has a substance in terms of knowledge

Strategies For Managing And Leading “The Millennial” In The Organization

Deborah Gilmurg in his article “Management Techniques for Bringing Out the Best in Generation Y” (2007) has detailed a about the management techniques for the millennial he is a specialist in generations dynamics and has offered a number of robust techniques that employers can implement in developing Generation Y.

Zinger in his article “Power of employee engagement” (2012) has detailed various ways to engage employee in the organization.

- Policies to be dynamic, created and implemented which reflects the needs of the millennia’s
- Need for connection to the outside world such as internal fun engagement, flex time, work from home, telecommuting and volunteer oppurtunites.
- Work at their speed, Gen Y has a sense of urgency hence organization needs to work at that pace rather than working at the pace of the organization.
- Develop reward programs which can be used as a vehicle for developing the talented Gen Y to grow quickly in fast track.
- Gen Y would like to buy and hear from Gen Y so create internal brand ambassadors and make the intranet as a vehicle to reach out to them
- Provide internal mentors who can help them to acclimated to the corporate world quickly again preferably a Gen Y mentor who can work with them at their pace.
- Communicate the big picture
- Provide clarity on their roles and responsibilities and how they can impact the business
- Interact with them frequently by various mechanism

- Design training program exclusively for the Gen Y – One size will not fit everyone.
- Provide experiential training rather than a class room training as it give hand on experience and mistakes can be experience in safe zone and successfully the knowledge can be transferred into the real work place
- Provide timely appreciation
- Implement programs to help Millennial develop greater problem-solving skills—skills that Generation Y employees often failed to develop in their early educational experiences. Filling the gap in these cognitive abilities is critical for helping Millennial succeed in meeting the strategic demands that the business will expect of them as they grow in the organization.”
- Create a fun, warm and friendly environment
- Develop and train the leaders so that they adapt and change their leadership style according to the need of the followers

Conclusion

It is very important for the organization to engage the millennia’s as they are 60% of the work force in the organization today, engaging them will help the organization to be more productive, efficient and effectiveness. Engaging these people and if the organization is able to ensure that high behavior and knowledge is demonstrated then the organization can gain a 20 years competitive advantage by influencing these workforce to be innovative and provide solutions which touches the human. Hence the organization should focus and use all the levers and mechanism to create engagement strategies to engage “The Millennial” and they can see the power that these engaged workforce brings to the work place.

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